

SUITABILITY OF OFFICE TECHNOLOGY AND MANAGEMENT GRADUATES AS PERCEIVED BY EMPLOYERS OF LABOUR IN POLYTECHNICS WITHIN NORTH EASTERN NIGERIA

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7936252>

Published Date: 15-May-2023

Abstract: The study titled suitability of Office Technology and Management Graduates as perceived by employers of labour in polytechnics within the North Eastern Nigeria was conducted to determine the suitability of Office Technology and Management graduates in today's office. The study was necessary in order to find out the perception of employers of labour on how suitable OTM graduates are in today's office. Two research questions and one null hypothesis guided the study. Descriptive survey research design was adopted. The population of the study was 330 employers of labour from polytechnics within north eastern Nigeria. 20 items structured questionnaire on a 4-point rating scale was used to draw data from respondents. The questionnaire was validated by three experts. Cronbach alpha reliability was used to test the reliability of the instrument and the coefficient was 0.89 showing that the instrument was highly reliable. The instrument was administered by the researchers and research assistants. Total number of 353 questionnaires were distributed, while 330 were retrieved constituting about 94% of the distributed questionnaires. Mean and Standard deviation were used to answer the research questions and t-test was used to test the null hypothesis, at 0.05 level of significance. The findings of the study revealed among others that employers of labour perceived that OTM graduates with sub-listed cognitive skills were suitable for today's world of work and these skills are what make OTM graduates to really display the real image of the organization. There was no significant difference in the opinions of more experienced and less experienced employers of labour and the opinions of employers of labour from federal polytechnics and their counterparts from the state polytechnics in North Eastern Nigeria, therefore the null hypothesis was accepted because the null hypothesis t-cals was less than t-table values. It was recommended among others that employers of labour in polytechnics within North Eastern Nigeria should list out suitable skills they perceived suitable for OTM graduates. If this is done, OTM graduates in polytechnics within North Eastern Nigeria will work towards that and thus be ready to cope with the routine office tasks.

Keywords: Suitability, Employers of Labour, Polytechnics, North-Eastern Nigeria, OTM Graaduates

1. INTRODUCTION

Background of the Study

Tertiary institutions in Nigeria produce many qualified graduates in different fields of study annually; virtually many of them become frustrated or despondent because they cannot secure jobs in the labour market. This accounts for the present upsurge of interest in vocational education as it affords graduates the privilege of processing employability skills. OTM as

an aspect of vocational education produce graduates with such utilized and laudable skills. Graduates of Office Technology and Management of tertiary institutions in Nigeria have high expectations after the end of their studies. The view is that their acquired skills after graduation should be able to open employment doors for them and they should not struggle like those in other unskilled fields who often grapple with unemployment. Employers feel that the return on employing graduates is low, given that graduates require substantial on-the-job training before they provide any returns to the firm. It is necessary for graduates to have a more realistic view of what they can offer and what they can expect from their first jobs, given their limited experiential training (Kelebogile 2014).

Unemployment rate among graduates of tertiary institutions remains one of the most noteworthy issues indicating the standards of living of most developing countries. There are some significant variations between what employers of labour want and the skills possessed by graduates, one of the ways to cope with this negative nasty circumstance of unemployment is to invest in self-learning and in the skills needed and suitable for the labor market (Mohammed, Vishanth, Nitham and Tillal 2019). Objectives of any career should not just be teaching, but in advance, tertiary institutions should expand the ways students engage with the world of work both within and outside of the curriculum by enhancing and expanding academic, social and personal competences suitable for employment. The engagement of tertiary institutions from one side helps the graduates to find themselves fit into labour market, to have a job and be suitable with the labour market requirements and from the other side helps employers of labour to find the right employees with the suitable skills they need (Turan,2017). All views above suggest the roles needed to be played by tertiary institutions in fulfilling the demand of the labour market on suitability of graduates of Office Technology and Management.

The reality is that Office Technology and Management graduates mostly have text book and theoretical knowledge which is not supported by sufficient practical work experience, in a country where the economy is not growing at a speed that allows for massive job creation, graduates find themselves faced with extended periods of unemployment. The preparedness of Office Technology and Management graduates for the workplace of multiple tasks and particularly their roles as image maker of the organization determine their suitability in today's office (Turan,2017).

The concept of suitability as it relates to graduates' employability has in recent time remained the focus of government, employers, job seekers and educators. Brown and Hesketh (2004) explain suitability as the relative chances of being appropriate for and retaining different kinds of employment. While most people view suitability in absolute term, focusing on the need for individual to obtain credential, knowledge and social status. The concept of suitability can also be seen as subjective and dependent on contextual factors. Suitability not only depends on whether one is able to fulfil the requirement of specific jobs, but also on how one stands relative to others in acceptance within the organization of job seekers (Brown and Hesketh. 2004). Asuquo and Agbolade (2014) defined suitability as a form of an active adjustment of individual towards certain occupation until they could identify and recognize existing career opportunities in the work place. It takes skill for a job seeker to be able to identify opportunities where others could not identify. Suitability in relation to graduates' employability can also be defined as a person's capability of gaining initial employment, maintaining employment and obtaining new employment if required (Asuquo and Agbolade, 2014). Suitability is the condition of being fitted for or appropriate for a job. It means the fitness of graduates to practice in that they are able to demonstrate, have the professional knowledge, skills and appropriate behavior to perform the job employed for (Tam, and Coleman (2009). It is of great importance that Office Technology and Management graduates be relevant, develop high skills and be suitable in today's office concentrated with innovations. Suitability therefore, connotes a person with an identifiable character, traits, skillful, appropriate, intelligent and conduct sufficient to decide the direction and trend of work. From the perception of employers, 'suitability' often seems to refer to 'work preparedness'; that is, having the skills, knowledge, attitudes and commercial understanding that will enable new graduates to make useful contributions to organizational purposes soon after commencing employment. (Mason, William and Cranmer 2009) (Turan, 2017).

Office Technology and Management (OTM) graduates are majorly from the Nigerian Polytechnic, the Nigerian Polytechnic system was designed for the training of office managers and office personnel. It was initially known as Secretarial Studies. Ogheneovo (2016) is of the opinion that it was designed by the National Board for Technical Education to substitute the Secretarial Studies programme. The new OTM programme was meticulously designed to cover various areas of study in several aspects of learning including humanities, management, social sciences, Information and Community Technology related fields, financial studies etc. The whole essence was to ensure that the graduates match expectations of contemporary development. Through the OTM programme, office managers are equipped for industries and the business world. Contemporary developments in the work places resulting from enhanced business practices and technicalities gave impetus

to the redesigning of the secretarial studies programmes. In order to ensure that contemporary expectations in the industries are met, various learning domains including cognitive, affective and psychomotor domains are meticulously explored and included in the curricular of National and Higher National Diplomas. OTM graduates are expected to be very versed in generic and specific areas as they are expected to handle multitasking

Perception, according to Hornby (2015) is the way you notice things, especially with the senses. It has much to do with an idea, a belief or image you have as a result of how you see or understand something. Perception is the process by which people select, organise, and interpret information to form a meaningful picture of the world. People can form different opinions of the same stimulus because of three perceptual processes; selective attention, selective distortion, and selective retention. People can be open to a great amount of stimuli every day. Sometimes it might be difficult for a person to pay attention to all these stimuli. Selective attention – the tendency for people to screen out most of the information to which they are exposed implies that amidst the myriads of information within the perceptive environment, certain aspects of the information attract attention. Selection distortion denotes that this information that attracted attention may not all be relevant in view of the mix. The screening involved selecting, integrating and organizing stimuli from the environment into a meaningful pattern. The screened and selected information is thus meant for the current memory. In the current memory the new information and previously acquired information may now be utilized to reach a decision. Retention is information that has been acquired and though not currently being utilised, it is stored and retained for specific and future use. All information that must be stored must go through the perception process.

For employers of labour to have a proper perception of the graduates of OTM, the perception process must have held sway. Those observable qualities which will eventually determine the Graduate Secretaries' performance indices will thus be perceived and noted and their suitability determined accordingly. Employers of labour in polytechnic includes: The Rector, Deputy Rector, Polytechnic Librarian, Bursar, Registrar, Director of Works, Deans of Schools and Head of departments within the polytechnics. They belong to the highest echelon of the employment cadre in the polytechnics.

The North East Nigeria is a geopolitical zone out the six geopolitical zones, representing both a geographic and political region of the country's northeast. It comprises of six states: Adamawa, Bauchi, Borno, Gombe, Taraba and Yobe (Saskia,2019)

Statement of the Problem

There have been numerous complaints about the quality of graduates produced in most tertiary institutions in Nigeria. Adebakin, Ajadi, and Subair (2014) observed that most graduates employed are not suitable for the post, some do not have critical skills and inclination to exhibit attributes that are necessary or suitable for the world of work.

The activities of Office Technology and Management Graduates in the past would have included reading mail as well as completing repetitive tasks that needed to be done in a more or less progressive fashion (Hao, Winston, Jarrod and Stephanie, 2014). This has changed as the arrival of modern technology in recent decades has increased not only the number of interruptions experienced (through multimedia devices) but also raised opportunities for higher levels of output (Lucas Jr, 2016). Office Technology and Management graduates of today are seen as multitasking personnel needed for achieving organizational goals. Duties undertaken by graduates of Office Technology and Management vary depending on the employer and level of education of the employee. Most duties of an office manager are performed through electronic means; and would normally include ordering and purchase approval of office supplies and services; hiring and supervision of front office workers; handling customer services; managing accounting functions; and often financial planning, analysing sales, and billing and record keeping along with physical distribution and logistics depending on the organization where they find themselves (Hines and Mercury, 2013).

The suitability and employability skills possessed by Office Technology and Management graduates should tally with what the employers of labour want. Some employers of labour have tried to outline some of these skills they want from job seekers. There are certain employability skills that are peculiar to Office Technology and Management graduates, for instance, secretarial skills and accounting skills remain relevant as ever as before. The degree to which Office Technology and Management graduates possess employability skills go a long way to determine their relevance and suitability in the world of work. The nature of routine tasks undertaken by Office Technology and Management graduates especially in contemporary business offices require cognitive skills, affective behavioural skills, technical skills and problem solving

skills and their suitability will go a long way to facilitating work. It is no wonder that all these skills are included in their various curricula. It is on this note that the researchers seek to examine the suitability of Office Technology and Management graduates as perceived by employers of labour in polytechnics within North Eastern Nigeria.

Employers of Labour Perceptions on Suitability skills needed by Office Technology and Management Graduates.

Employers of labour perceived the following as skills suitable for OTM graduates who really want to be the best in their fields of endeavor:

Transferable skills

To start a new career, an Office Technology and Management graduate need transferable skill. Transferable skill are all skills that can be taken from one job to another. It is the ability to clearly communicate ideas to others, solve unexpected problems, or work well in a team and decision within one's jurisdiction (Dale,2022). Transferable skills combine competencies, knowledge and skill that have been gained from school, internships or elsewhere to next employment or career. The importance of transferable skills is increasingly emphasized in recent times by employers of labour most especially as it relates to OTM graduates, they are expected to transfer what they have learnt in the four walls of the classroom to be fully practiced when employed. The pressure of global competition means that OTM graduates need to offer an employer more than academic skills traditionally represented by the subject and class of degree. It has been the demand from employers of labour that graduates would gladly transfer what they have learnt to solve real problem encountered in today's office. Most bosses always want their secretaries to display high level of diplomacy and initiative in sensitive matters arising from each day task. It is at this stage that an OTM graduate will definitely know that office work requires high level of diplomacy wherein it is needed to apply what they have learn to real life situation. For instance, in Office Application students learn about Microsoft Word and Microsoft Excel, these are needed when employed to work in any office of today (Muhammed, 2012)

Attitude

Attitude refers to a set of emotion, beliefs and behavior towards object, person or event. Attitudes can also be as a result of experience or upbringing of an individual. Attitude can have a powerful influence over behavior and affect how people act in various situations or to life situation. While attitudes are enduring, they can also change (Kendra, 2022). OTM graduates with a good attitude has range of thoughts regarding their employment. They are constantly looking for better approaches to solving problems and ways to enhance a workplace that will benefit everyone within the organization. Employers of labour will definitely love to see OTM graduates with good attitudes willing to perform excellently and demonstrate a high level of pride in what they accomplished or how they can improve the environment around them. Employer of labour love to see OTM graduate that can get along with customers/ clients with the ability to enter conversation with positive attitudes and are able to handle business in a professional manner, as well as being approachable and easy to deal with on a regular basis. This statement goes with the popular saying that "first impression lasts long", therefore employers expected that OTM graduates make best impression possible, so that customers will have good impression about such organization. OTM graduates should know that good attitude opens many doors of opportunities in life both in career and personal life (Rea, 2016).

Time Management and Organization

Time management is a way in which an employee organizes and plans time to carry out specific activities. Effective time management boosts productivity that is a task can be completed in less time, even when working under pressure. It is about planning, minimizing distraction and carrying out regular reviews to make sure that progress is made. The significant factor in time management is prioritization and it is only with practice that an employee can learn to prioritize task more effectively, focusing on the most urgent task rather than less important activities (Lawrence, Raivo and Abdessamad, 2011).

Work Ethic and Dependability

Having a strong work ethic is often part of what an employer of labour values in an employee. It is based on a personal understanding of taking pride in work rather than the reward attach to such work. The act of demonstrating a positive approach to work and being honest as well as taking initiative and caring about co-worker are all factors that convey a

strong work ethic. In addition to this, learning new skills, showing a commitment to your employer and being responsible to work even when things do not go as expected or planned all illustrate a good work ethic. There are values/norms in every profession that make employees fit/suitable for a choice of career (Dale, 2022).

Attention to detail

Creating an error free work is important and make OTM graduates suitable in many organizations. So an eye for details is a skill that can be used in almost all job. OTM graduates who can pay attention to details will have ability to spot errors in their works which can save costly mistake and ensure that all output is completed to highest standards whether in preparing memos, and all forms of correspondences (Dale, 2022).

Communication Skill

Johnson, (2022), sees communication skill as the ability to communicate effectively and as a useful skill in any career or any field. It encompasses numerous things including how to listen and reflect what one hears, how to resolve conflict and how to relay ideas and points with clarity and brevity. Employers of labour love to work with OTM graduates that can work on articulating ideas and viewpoints through writing and in impromptu conversation and can collaborate with others. Employers of labour want graduates with presentation skill who can share ideas with audience and writing skills that is writers who can write eligibly and present ideas in concise form. They love to work with good writers who can use active voice and avoid terminology that customers/clients are likely to understand.

Workplace Etiquettes

Miller (2022), put workplace etiquette as behavior in the work place, for making the environment where people work a polite, respectful and pleasant place to be. Many employers of labour are meticulous about workplace etiquettes, they always want employees to arrive early especially OTM graduates who are expected to be in the office before the boss and stay until after the boss leaves and ready to complete tasks on time with standard. Employers of labour wants graduates who are ready to take challenges in task not directly related to their area of specialization and would not decline whatever task given to them but rather excited in taking any opportunities (Richinick, 2020).

Objective of the Study

The main objective of the study is to determine the suitability of Office Technology and Management graduates as perceived by employers of labour in polytechnic within the North Eastern Nigeria.

Specifically, the study was designed:

1. To assess the perception of employers of labour on Cognitive Skills suitable for OTM graduates in polytechnics within the North eastern Nigeria
2. To examine the perception of employers of labour on Affective Behavioral Skills suitable for OTM graduates in polytechnics within the North eastern Nigeria.

Research Questions

1. In what ways do employers of labour perceive OTM graduates' cognitive skills as suitable in the Polytechnics within the North Eastern Nigeria?
2. In what ways do employers of labour perceive the OTM graduates' affective behavior skills as suitable in the Polytechnics within the North Eastern Nigeria?

Hypothesis

H₀₁: There is no significance difference in the mean responses of more experienced and less experienced employers of labour on the suitability of Office Technology and Management Graduates in polytechnics within North Eastern Nigeria.

2. METHODS

The study was descriptive survey design and was carried out in Taraba state, Nigeria. The population used for the study comprised of employers of labour from polytechnics within North Eastern Nigeria, comprising of 330 employers of labour. There was no sampling technique adopted because all were used for the study due to the manageable size of the population.

Questionnaire was the instrument used to gather data for the study. The instrument consists of ten question items for each research question seeking information on the on the suitability of OTM graduates as perceived by employers of labour. The Instrument was validated by 3 experts in Office Technology and Management. For the purpose of analysis, values were assigned to the four options provided in the instrument as follows: Very Suitable (VS)= 4 marks with boundary of 3.50-4.00, Suitable(S) = 3 marks with boundary limit of 3.00-3.49; Fairly Suitable (FS) = 2 marks with boundary limit of 2.50-2.99 and Not Suitable(NS) = 1 mark with boundary limit of 1.50-2.49 for the two research questions. Arithmetic Mean was used to analyze the data collected. A minimum of 2.5 mean score was set at standard for relevance or otherwise of the research question raised on the study. Any research question scored below the set standard was not suitable. If t-test calculated value is less than t test critical value, accept null hypothesis or otherwise reject.

Research Question One: In what ways do employers of labour perceive OTM graduates' cognitive skills as suitable in the Polytechnics within the North Eastern Nigeria?

Table 1: Mean and Standard Deviation on responses on suitable cognitive skills by OTM graduates

S/N	Item Statements	X	SD	Remark
1	Ability to look, listen and think about work place tasks over a while is a suitable cognitive skill	3.59	1.89	Very Suitable
2	Ability to respond to direction (response inhibition) at the work place when there is sudden distraction is suitable cognitive skill	3.26	1.81	Suitable
3	Ability to process incoming information without supervision is suitable cognitive skill	3.41	1.85	Suitable
4	Multitasking with success involving simultaneous attention between one or more activities is what employers of labour find suitable	3.34	1.83	Suitable
5	Organizing concepts and information form suitable cognitive skill for OTM graduates	3.30	1.82	Suitable
6	A unique ability of an OTM graduate to figure out pattern and find out logical solutions is an aspect of suitable cognitive skill.	3.25	1.80	Suitable
7	Ability to quickly perform mental tasks is an aspect of cognitive skills suitable for OTM graduates.	3.4	1.84	Suitable
8	Logic and reasoning skills that help in solving problems is a suitable cognitive skills.	2.47	1.57	Not Suitable
9	Ability to pay attention to instruction is a suitable skill for OTM graduates	3.5	1.87	Very Suitable
10	Ability to record, store and recall information are suitable cognitive skills perceived as adequate for OTM graduates	3.42	1.85	Suitable

Source: Field Survey, 2023

Table 1 showed that the respondents indicated 'suitable' for seven (7) item constructs, two (2) for very suitable and one (1) for not suitable. Mean ranging from 2.47 to 3.59. The table showed that the respondents indicated that most of the items listed were suitable cognitive skills possessed by OTM graduates under the employment of polytechnics within North Eastern Nigeria. It was stated that the graduates exhibit these skills in their daily office tasks. The mean of the responses were all above 2.50 implying that the constructs were all suitable except one item with indicating not suitable. All the items have standard deviations ranging from 1.57 to 1.89. Take for example, item number 4 (four)in the table that stated thus: Multitasking and paying attention seem to be one major thing employers of labour would want more to be displayed by OTM graduates. The entire items portray the obvious showing that the amount of measurements in the set did not significantly vary from the average for the set.

Research Question Two: In what ways do employers of labour perceive the OTM graduates' affective behavior skills as suitable in the Polytechnics within the North Eastern Nigeria?

Table 2: Mean and Standard Deviation on responses on suitable Affective Behavioral skills by OTM graduates

S/N	Item Statements	X	SD	Remark
1	Empathy listening and following instruction and excellent communication skills are aspect of affective behavioural skill suitable for OTM graduates	3.62	1.90	Very Suitable
2	Conflict resolution is one of the most behavioural skills suitable for today's world of work.	3.22	1.79	Suitable
3	Unsatisfied curiosity as well as a persistent attitude towards self-improvement is among the suitable behavioral skills to get along in workplace.	3.24	1.8	Suitable
4	Stress management is a suitable affective behavioural skill every OTM graduate should possess.	3.21	1.79	Suitable
5	Patience to hold on to one's emotion and personal grouse is an affective behavioural conduct in workplace	3.30	1.82	Suitable
6	Awareness or sensibility to understand other people's emotions and feelings from their point of view play suitable roles in building strong team among OTM graduates	3.35	1.83	Suitable
7.	Ability to maintain good social networking makes room for optimal performance by employees.	3.26	1.80	Suitable
8	Emotional intelligence which is an aspect of affective behavioural skills help in managing stress without overreacting and is perceived as suitable for OTM graduates.	3.33	1.82	Suitable
9	Work ethic as an overall attitude helps OTM graduates put their best at work and it is suitable.	3.30	1.81	Suitable
10	Collaboration skills that helps to work efficiently with other employees is a suitable affective behavioral skills	3.33	1.82	Suitable

Source: Field Survey, 2023

Table 2 showed that the respondents indicated 'suitable' for nine (9) item constructs and one (1) for very suitable. Mean ranging from 3.21 to 3.62. The table showed that the respondents indicated that all items listed were suitable affective behavioural skills possessed by OTM graduates under the employment of polytechnics within North Eastern Nigeria. It was stated that the graduates exhibit these skills in their daily office tasks. The mean of the responses were all above 2.50 implying that the constructs were all suitable. All the items have standard deviation ranging from 1.79 to 1.90. Take for example, item number 1 (one) in the table that stated thus: listening and paying attention is one of the skills that can help OTM graduates have a hitch free relationship with employers of labour within the Polytechnic in North Eastern Nigeria.

H₀₁: There is no significance difference in the mean responses of more experienced and less experienced employers of labour on the suitability of Office Technology and Management Graduates in polytechnics within North Eastern Nigeria.

Variables	N	Mean	SD	Df	t-cal	t- table	Decision
More Experienced	182	2.30	1.52	328	1.48	1.96	Not Sig.
Less Experienced	148	2.12	1.46				

Source: Field Survey, 2023

The table above showed that t-cal (1.48) is less than t-table (at 0.05 level of significance). Therefore, the null hypothesis is accepted. This indicates that there was no significant difference in the opinions of more experienced and less experienced employers of labour on the suitability of Office Technology and Management Graduates in polytechnics within North Eastern Nigeria.

3. DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

1. On suitable cognitive skills perceived by employers of labour in the polytechnics within North Eastern Nigeria, the finding revealed that employers of labour perceived that OTM graduates with sub-listed cognitive skills like (listening and thinking, Multi-tasking skill, finding logical solutions, ability to quickly perform mental tasks, paying attention to instruction and so on) were suitable for today's world of work. These skills are what make OTM graduates to really display the real image of an organization. Employers of labour would always want OTM graduates take initiative in areas that needed diplomacy and tasks. This is in line with the study of Suleman (2016) who reported that employers required broad cluster skills from graduates, namely foundation skills that include written and oral communication, problem solving, ability to adapt to new situation, interpersonal skills, coping with pressure and stress, meeting with deadlines and critical analysis. Potgieter and Coetzee (2013) corroborated this assertion in their study they infer that a person disposition affects his suitability in the place of work, a graduate with good personality would stand out among others and would be able to withstand the stress of today's world of work. All these skills put together are in great demand and employers of labour are satisfied with these skills in graduate.

2. OTM graduates with suitable affective behavior as listed in research question two, will have high level of achieving more in the place of work. Employers of labour get to go along with OTM graduates that can manage stress, demonstrate sensible conducts, communicates well with students (polytechnic students) client, have good emotional intelligence and that can persevere with others. OTM graduates with suitable affective behavioral skills will have optimal performance display overall attitude that employers of labour would cherish most. The study is in line with the report of Lorraine and Qualer (2023) that emotional intelligence which is an aspect of affective behavioural skills is significantly related to suitability of graduates. Graduates with high emotional intelligence are more confident in their ability to perceive, use, understand and have good personal network with other colleagues. A graduate who is emotionally competent is seen as an effective communicator with colleagues, employers of labour, students/clients.

4. CONCLUSION

From the findings of the study it was concluded as follows:

In research question one, all items listed were seen suitable by employers of labour and an OTM graduates with these listed cognitive skills will find office job to be easy and would be seen as a reliable office administrator. In today's office going by the finding of the researchers, office environment needs OTM with suitable cognitive skills like responding to direction, good record/recalling ability and so on. It was concluded that an OTM graduate with high level of cognitive skills will be able to comprehend and understand many office tasks at any level or time.

Research question two discussed on behavior affective skills. The respondents' opinions indicated that the listed skills were suitable in the perception of the employers of labour. The researchers concluded that affective behavioural skills can be seen as one of the skill that present an OTM graduate suitable or fit into the work environment. Apart from the boss (es) that is seen as the chief executive, the next set of person who can still represent the image of the office is an OTM graduate. This one of the main reason why OTM graduates are seen as the reflection of an organization that is why OTM graduates emotional intelligence go a long way to proof the image of an organization when they come in contact in clients/customers/students.

5. RECOMMENDATIONS

The followings recommendations were proffered from the results of the study by the researchers:

1. Since employers of labour perceived the suitability of cognitive skills listed, it is obvious that OTM graduates should improve more on these skills and other related cognitive skills. By doing this, OTM graduates in polytechnics within North eastern Nigeria will able to enjoy office tasks than other colleagues from other field of works.

2. Employers of labour in polytechnics within the North Eastern Nigeria should list out suitable skills they perceived suitable for OTM graduates. If this is done, OTM graduates in polytechnics within North Eastern Nigeria will work towards that and thus be ready to cope with the routine office tasks.

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